

Compliance of commercial establishments in Metro Manila, Philippines towards Republic Act No. 9211 and the Food and Drugs Authority Circular No. 2019-006

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Abstract

Laws are designed to keep things in order, thus, preventing people for actions that may lead to chaos and may harm others. With the increasing number of cases that involves businesses and juveniles, this study aims to determine their compliance on Republic Act No. 9211, Section 9, and portions of the FDA Circular No. 2019-006 that states the prohibition of selling alcoholic beverages to minors. Through a descriptive-quantitative research approach and the use of a survey questionnaire data needed have been gathered, discussed, and interpreted. Results show that majority of the respondents are aware that they are prohibited by the law to buy alcoholic beverages, however, still do it, as ordered by a family member or friend in most cases and for their own consumption occasionally. It was also discovered that frequently, when minors try to buy alcoholic beverages, vendors/cashiers just ask them what they wish to buy and let them pay for it without verifying their age, which is usually observed in Sari-Sari Stores and Convenience stores as minors tend to purchase such products on these types of stores more often. Moreover, majority of the respondents have been determined to have experienced being allowed and not being permitted by the vendors/cashiers to purchase liquors in supermarkets, convenience stores, and sari-sari stores, however, it has been found out that the frequency of minors being allowed to purchase such products were higher than instances when they were prohibited in sari-sari stores and convenience stores compared in supermarket where the frequency of incidents where minors were not permitted is higher. Furthermore, the highest frequency of such incidents has been recorded in sari-sari stores. Nevertheless, all these types of stores have been determined as non-compliant with the law and policy, hence, should undergo investigation, which will eventually lead to interventions that would ensure compliance to the law.

Keywords: Law; Alcoholic beverages; Business; Juvenile.

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Introduction

Parts of the society are laws and policies that people needs to abide. These are rules and regulations designed to keep things in order, thus, preventing people for actions that may lead to chaos and may harm others. According to Cerna (2013), policies are the outlines of what the government is planning to do and what do not intend to do for the betterment of the society. It evolves the principles and practices that are needed for achieving the goal. Meanwhile, policies and laws are not the same, however, these policies can lead to the enforcement of a new law. Laws on the other hand refer to set of standards, principles, and procedures that must be followed in society to keep things in order. A law is primarily made for implementing justice in the society; there are various types of laws such as criminal laws, civil laws, and international laws among others, and each type has its own degree of apprehension to violators. While a law is framed for bringing justice to the society, a policy is framed for achieving certain goals. Though are different in definition, both has the same nature, and that is to inform people what is okay and what is not.

In the Philippines, there are three branches of government; the executive, the judiciary, and the legislative. The executive is the law-enforcing body, the judiciary is the law-interpreting body, while the legislative is law-making body, thus, this shows that laws are really part of what a country is and the people's lives. This is how important laws and policies are. There are a several laws and policies in the country; however, one cannot deny the fact that there are instances where it is not being obeyed and not being implemented well. Juvenile crimes for example is prevalent, likewise, businesses that do not comply with the standards. Between 2018 and 2020 numerous businesses including a convenience store have been shut down after getting to caught operating without a business permit (Orellana, 2019; Leyson, 2017; Kabagani, 2020), additionally, several businesses and employers including industry giants have been complained to the Department of Labor and Employment, 3,377 to be exact, which have been determined to violate the labor code (De Vega, 2018). Violations of laws involving minors on the other hand as been a major problem of the land as well over the years; as cited in an article by The Manila Times (2019), the Philippine National Police-Women and Children Protection Center revealed that the number of delinquency committed by minors in 2019 was higher by nearly 8% compared with the data recorded in 2018, thus, aside from the changes from minor to more violent crimes, minors' involvement in illegal doings has increased significantly over the years. Meanwhile, aside from deaths, these youth groups have committed several delinquencies, hence, instilling fear among residents; in one Tuesday night at another barangay in Metro Manila, a member of a gang robbed a woman of some P33,200 worth of valuables (Marquez, 2019).

After learning that there have been several cases of law violations among minors and businesses, the researcher through this study aims to determine the compliance of establishments to one of the most unexplored laws and policies in the field of research as it has been determined that there is dearth of studies on this - the Republic Act No. 9211, Section 9, and portions of the FDA Circular No. 2019-006 that states the prohibition of selling alcoholic beverages to minors.

Rationale

Laws and policies are important, and so are studies that discuss it. This study will not only find out whether the selected businesses are compliant with the law or not, but this will also lead to interventions by authorities to ensure that these law and policy are observed and is being able serve its purposes. This will also lead to further studies and might be a way also to recognize laws that are not being followed yet still written on the books, hence, useless.

Research Problem and Objectives

As studies and public records suggest, there have been a number of cases where businesses and minors have violated laws, hence, the inspiration of this study. This study focuses on determining the compliance of establishments to Republic Act No. 9211, Section 9, and portions of the FDA Circular No. 2019-006 that states the prohibition of selling alcoholic beverages to minors with an aim to suggest interventions to strengthen laws and policies and get things in order in the community level.

Literature Review

Alcohol consumption is the world's most frequently used psychoactive drug, one of the major causes of mortality and handicap. Alcohol consumption is responsible for 3.2% of all fatalities globally every year and also represents 4.0% of the world's burden on diseases yearly. Research showed that alcohol consumption is linked to alcohol dependency, other use of medicinal material, unintentional injury, physical combat, crime, suicide and attempting and increased HIV-AIDS risk.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recently made a global decrease in hazardous alcohol use a priority in addressing this global public health problem. Even with inadequate statistics, it is nevertheless obvious, as a result of increased use of alcohol and insufficient or nonexistent regulations and initiatives for prevention, that medium or low-income nations have a disproportionate public health burden (WHO, 2019).

A variety of psychological and environmental variables affects the consumption of alcohol in young people. In recent studies, the importance of exposure to alcohol commercialization and its impact on young people in particular are being highlighted. However, such study has, with a few exceptions, been confined to high-income countries. Research on the alcohol predictors and their negative results for young people in the Philippines is uncommon. WHO data showed that almost 9% of the Philippines aged 15 and over (estimated at 86 million) had a problem with alcohol consumption. Moreover, 25% of men and 8.3% of women (+15-85 years) are heavy-drinkers. The function of alcohol marketing and its possible relation to early use among young people is a related, but also largely ignored concern throughout the wider western Pacific area, particularly the Philippines.

There has been growing concern since the 1990s about the damage associated with heavy drinking and alcohol and the association with the rise of the marketing of alcohol for youth.

Liquor Purchase of Minors

The Asian alcohol industry analyst has described ready-to-drink beverages as a beginning point for youthful drinkers going from drinks to soft drinks, says Swahn et al. (2013). In the Philippines, women and new young drinkers are expected to grow in RTDs. RTD's marketing in the Philippines started to be small-scale, but sales rose considerably when local businesses started to compete with Diageo Philippines Inc.'s import brands. Global alcohol firms including Diageo, Heineken, Carlsberg, Anheuser Busch, SABMiller and Kirin have intensive rivalry to position themselves to take part in the Western Pacific developing markets. Recent company reports from global alcohol companies show that the goal is to target young countries that are growing. In two of the very few studies conducted on the exposure to alcohol marketing among young people in a low-income nation, findings indicate that alcohol marketing is rather prevalent in Zambia (20%) and among vulnerable young people in Uganda (27 percent) (in 2016). Previous studies largely carried out in North America and Europe showed that the risk of alcohol consumption in teenagers has increased by exposure to alcohol ads and the possession of alcohol promotional products. It is also evident that the marketing of alcohol, based on considerable research, also impacts young people's attitudes and views about alcohol that are linked to their anticipations and intents to drink alcohol. Furthermore, young people who report alcohol ads are more likely to use alcohol. The long-term effect of alcohol marketing exposure is more problematic. Exposure to alcohol advertising in young people, for instance, forecasts young people's alcohol usage intentions until two years later.

In addition, according to Swahn et al. (2014), the entirety of earlier research indicates that alcohol marketing to young people is an ever-growing concern for public health and that young people living in countries with a limited policy on alcohol and self-regulation by the alcohol industry may exacerbate this problem. This may be due to the available resources to support marketing activities in the alcohol sector. Alcohol Justice is a group focused largely to the alcohol and marketing sector in the US (previously the Marin Institute). They claim that the alcohol sector spends over 6 billion dollars annually to promote its products. Unfortunately, many alcohol marketing techniques directly target young people. Special worries arise from the fact that parents can usually protect their children against exposures, which include billboards, ads on sport events and concerts, buildings, newspapers, magazines and on internet. However, in recent years expenditure has grown by trillions on various forms of marketing called out-of-home advertising. The promotion and marketing of alcohol products significantly enhances intention and actual use of alcohol in young people. Moreover, new research has shown that young people are more exposed than adults to alcohol marketing and need better protection. The growing usage of digital media is exacerbating the situation. The alcohol marketers utilize their campaigns quickly through social networking and young people use such media more strongly to worsen their exposure to marketing alcohol (Swahn et al., 2013).

Liquor Selling of Establishments to Minors

According to Acosta (2018), the use or possession or unauthorized sale of minors and or volatile materials for inducing intoxication or, in any manner changer, distortion or disturbance of the auditory, visual and mental process is forbidden pursuant to Sections 3 and 4 of Presidential Decree (PD) 1619. The establishment or shop may nevertheless be responsible under PD 1619 to sell liquors to minors, despite the fact that the shops or establishments have not broken any ordinance or legislation governing the distance to be followed between the shop and the school. The Republic Act 938 regulates regulating the sale of liquors within a radius of two hundred linear meters, from schools and universities, by shops and other facilities. The use, possession or illegal sale to minors or volatile chemicals for the aim of inducing or in any way affecting or distorting the auditory, visual and or mental process is banned in accordance with Sections 3 and 4 of Presidential Decree 169.

In the study by Swahn et al., (2013), which examines alcohol marketing and drunkenness among Philippine students, there is a substantial alcohol marketing exposure and that alcohol consumption and drunkenness in school attenders in the Philippines are related with this exposure. These findings stress the need for leaders to emphasize policies to restrict alcohol exposure and to restrict the practices of alcohol marketing as essential preventative measures to reduce alcohol consumption and its harmful health effects for young people in the Philippines. Media exposure helps impact the societal norm of drinking via a variety of ways, including films, television, social media and other entertainment, through advertising, product placements and storytelling. Although selling and marketing of alcohol are strictly controlled, consumers, particularly in the Philippines, are exposed to a broad range of alcohol and liquor promotional products (Sudhinaraset et al., 2016). It was the subject of numerous public policy discussions and a lot of alcohol and consumer research that these advertising led to direct increases in consumption. Recent studies have utilized strong methodological approaches to evaluate the alcohol consumption impacts of advertising (Grenard et al., 2013).

Albeit longitudinal research have indicated that alcohol advertising especially affects the prone to alcohol in younger adolescents (Grenard et al., 2013), the random assignment of college students to alcohol advertising shows no differences with the control group (Koordeman et al., 2018). The impacts of advertising are expected to vary between age groups and races. Empirical research demonstrate that focused alcohol marketing leads to the development of favorable views about drinking and the creation and development of environmentally friendly and promoted alcohol usage (Alaniz & Wilkes, 1998 as cited in Berey et al., 2017). These variables can lead to drinking and binge drinking and an increased consumption of alcohol (Tanski et al., 2011). Moreover, San Miguel Beer (SMB) is a favorite alcoholic beverage in the Philippines according to Valbuena (2006). A beer made locally, its name is slowly and profoundly ingrained in the Filipino mind, and in the Philippines it has become a generic word for beer. Its target market not only includes C-D revenue brackets, but also corporate market targets. In 1997, San Miguel Corporation (SMC) invested 15.2 million dollars in advertising, making it the country's seventh largest advertiser. Positive pictures are depicted in the Philippines for beer and liquors. SMC has diverse tactics which focus on core Filipino values depending on which market they wish to reach.

Beer and other drinks have, among many others, been linked to sedation, male bonding, friendship and friendship, togetherness, youthfulness and enjoyment. The popular local action and seductive actors and actresses as their pictorial models are the most prevalent in ads. In addition, increasing usage of social media for alcohol marketing has led to corresponding changes in teenage and college youth communication strategies (Hoffman et al. 2018). Marketing tactics for a variety of items reflect research that might affect teenagers' behaviour (Cook et al., 2005). Social media sites are utilized most often by young people with 92 percent reporting online and 24 percent reporting online "almost continuously" (Lenhart, 2015). Social websites such as Twitter, Instagram and Facebook have a commercial connection with alcohol. One research revealed that more than 1,000 Facebook-related alcohol sites were available in 2012 (Nhean et al., 2014). Use of alcohol grows as the internet links and peer density increases, a degree of social network connectivity (Cook et al., 2013). Although rules have been self-imposed to block young people from access, more than two-thirds of YouTube advertising has been made available to young people under legal drinking age, alcohol advertising (Barry et al., 2018).

Christmas is a great time, but these joyous days can also pose health concerns. This is because around this time of year alcohol consumption increases. According to Dr. Diana A. Payawal of the Philippine Society of Gastroenterology, alcohol consumption is prevalent during Christmas during the health forum "Malusog na Katawan Ngayong Kapaskuhan" (proper intake of alcohol, nutrition and diet, and medication conformity) hosted in the Philippine Physician's College. Payawal also referenced a Holiday Drinking Facts survey, which showed that 96% went after a vacation party to work with a hangover or knew anybody who had. In the same survey, 60 percent believe that alcohol plays a party; 57% observe individuals driving under alcohol and, 40 percent said they use the vacation as an excuse to drink, together with their friends and family members.

In terms of rum consumption (liters per person) and number one in Asia, Payawal cited the Philippines as placing the world's third-largest. In terms of beer consumption, the country is the world's top gin consumers (liters per person) and 7th in Asia. Southeast Asia also ranked second in terms of alcohol consumption in the Philippines. The common rate of alcohol use in a population of 90 million is approximated at 5 million Filipino drinkers (Mocon-Ciriaco, 2020).

Knowledge and Awareness of Minors to Age Requirement to Buy Liquors

Valbuena (2006) reports that consuming alcoholic beverages above our ability to poison is a dangerous activity, which most young individuals engage in. 5.3 million Filipino young people are known to be drinking alcoholic drinks in the survey performed by the University of the Philippines in 1994, whereas some 4.2 million are men and 1.1 million are women. The survey showed that most Philippine adolescents tried smokes, alcohol and medicines. Actually, more drinkers than smokers are alcoholic. The Philippines, on average, begin to drink alcohol around 16 or 17 years of age. However, adolescents under the age of 12 already drink alcoholic drinks are also frequent. About 37% of the poll respondents continued to drink alcohol, whilst 33% stated they drank only alcohol on exceptional occasions. About 17% indicated they decided to stop the drinking habit. Drinking among girls is more accepted than smoking in the Philippines.

This is still the case, however, that males are regarded better than women to drink. Parents are laxer with children than their sisters, so that they are freer to drink alcohol. The young people stated they were persuaded by their family, friends and the media to try with alcohol. The young people tend to take their lead from attitudes and actions, emphasizing the essential role that families play in juvenile conduct. It is more likely that a boy who is growing up with an alcoholic father is one. The survey showed that the most likely to drink are those who might not live with their parents, permitted by the parents to drink, often attend social meetings and parties, and those who are not involved in sports.

Philippine legislation establishes the minimum legal age of drinking at 18. Most young individuals receive alcohol with or without the approval of their parents. You know how to get alcohol - you can get it from friends, or you can buy it secretly. The 1997 Household Income and Expenditure Survey show that an average Philippine family spends one percent of their income on alcoholic drinks. However, if a minimum wage employee, for example, receives \$5 a day, and becomes used to bearing at least three drink bottles of beer every night, this means spending \$1 a day on beer that already accounts for 20 percent of his hard paid money. The Philippines' joyful activities include alcohol consumption. Beer is a major element of festivities, celebrations and birthdays. Even though there is no particular opportunity, a lot of Philistines gather around, drinking gin and tonic that is a much cheaper alcohol drink in the streets and in shops. That is particularly true for a low-income population in which, unlike individuals who have money to hang out and drink from middle- and high-income groups. Drinks at the bars are around 100% cheaper. There appears to be a substantial link between alcohol use in adolescents and numerous social, emotional and behavioral issues such as using illicit substances, fighting, theft, drugs, skipping, feeling depressed and trying purposefully to injure or kill yourself. Along with the adolescent issues, alcohol-related disorders are associated with early starting in life later on. A study revealed that the early use of alcohol (i.e., by 12 years of age) was connected to subsequent alcohol addiction and related problems in later adolescence, including alcohol aggression, wounds, drinking and driving, school absences and an increased risk of other substances (Gruber et al., 1996). Another study revealed that those who start drinking before the age of 15 are 4 times more prone to alcohol dependency than those who start drinking after the age of 21 (Dawson et al., 2012). Consequently, the postponement of start of alcohol consumption among young adolescents to their present and long-term health is obviously an essential objective of public health.

In addition, the causes for the first time must be identified in order to design successful programs to prevent alcohol consumption by early adolescents. According to the Triadic Influence theory (TTI) that incorporates several behavioral theories in a comprehensive health behavior "mega-theory," all behaviors have origins in three areas: personal qualities of an individual, present social situation and cultural environment (Petraitis et al., 1995). For certain circumstances, the TTI also identifies varying levels of behavioral impact. For example, proximal variables directly concern the drinker (i.e.) while distal factors are related to the surroundings of the drinker (e.g., parental practices or laws and policies influencing access to alcohol).

Personal, social and environmental variables have been repetitively shown to be related with drinking in teenagers in accordance with TTI (Komro et al., 2005). Personal factors that promote alcohol use include rebellion, tolerance of transgression, strong value for independence and non-compliance, poor educational dedication and performance, positive belief and attitudes to alcohol consumption and a lack of efficiency in denying alcohol offers. Social influences that promote adolescent consumption include low socioeconomic status and low parenting, family disruptions, conflicts, weak family relationships, low parental supervision, parental leave and lack of rules on alcohol consumption, alcohol family history, peer alcohol consumption, perceived adult authorization, and perceived peer approval. The legal, economic and physical availability of alcohol and the cultural norms relating to the use of alcohol are important environmental factors for teenage consumption.

In the analysis conducted out by Komro (2018), researchers and clinicians have to continue identifying the most important features of various intervention strategies that contribute to the effectiveness of these strategies and develop a comprehensive approach to the prevention of adolescent alcohol consumption. The following sections and the table provide a summary of current information on the most promising elements of the entire range of preventative measures, including the education and training, family, policy and community initiatives. Knowledge of efficient measures to decrease underage drinking has increased considerably during the last decade, notably in school-based programs addressing individual characteristics, and researchers have identified important components for state-of-the-art school-based programs. However, these initiatives alone are unlikely to result in continuous decreases in minors' drinking. School-based programs should instead be integrated with non-curricular initiatives, family and policy which contribute to changing the entire social and cultural context in which young people live, creating a persistent drop in consumption and alcohol-related issues in youth. Although important components have been identified of non-scholastic tactics, additional study into many of these areas is needed to fully understand what variables need to be targeted and what approaches can best meet these objectives and minimize drinking among young individuals. In order to become more aware of each method, researchers, doctors and policy-makers must integrate this information, developing high-quality, complementary projects that, combined, generate treatments that are sufficient to combat the beverage culture present in Philippine communities.

Synthesis

The most widely used psychoactive substance in the world is the use of alcohol and is one of the main causes of death and disability. Annually, alcohol consumption accounts for 3.2% of all deaths worldwide, and it is also 4.0% of the world's disease burden annually. Research has shown that alcoholic drinking is connected to dependence on alcohol, other usage of medical products, involuntary injuries, physical fighting, crimes, and suicides, even higher risk of HIV-AIDS. In tackling the worldwide challenge of public health, the World Health Organization (WHO) lately prioritized a global decline in alcohol usage. Even if data were not enough it is nonetheless evident that medium- and low-income countries have a disproportionate public health burden, due to increased use of alcohol and insufficient or non-existent laws and preventative measures.

Furthermore, Swahn et al. (2013) reported that all previous study shows the rising concern for public health of young people to sell alcohol and that young people living in countries with restricted alcohol and alcohol self-regulation policies may worsen the problem. This may be owing to the resources available to fund alcohol marketing initiatives. In addition, new study has indicated that young people are more exposed to and need stronger protection than adults to commercial alcohol. Digital media are increasingly becoming more and more used. Alcoholics marketers adopt social networking tools rapidly and young people use such sites to make their exposure to marketing alcohol worse (Swahn et al., 2018).

Republic Law 938 restricts the sale of liquors from schools and colleges, businesses and other institutions in a radius of two hundred linear meters. In line with Sections 3 and 4 of Presidential Decrees 169, use, possession or unlawful sale of minors or volatile substances to induce or alter the auditory, visual and or mental process. Although longitudinal study has shown that alcohol advertising impacts younger teenagers in particular (Grenard et al., 2013), there are no differences with the control group for alcohol random assignments of college students (Koordeman et al., 2012 as cited in Esser & Jennigan, 2018). The impacts of advertising between age groups and races are likely to differ. Empirical study shows that targeted alcohol marketing leads to pleasant drinking opinions and the growth and development of ecologically friendly and promoted use of alcohol (Alaniz & Wilkes, 1998 as cited in Berey et al., 2017).

In recent decades, knowledge of effective strategies to lower minor drinking has significantly expanded and the researchers identified key components of state-of-the-art, school-based programs in particular. These measures alone, however, are unlikely to lead to a sustained drop in drinking among children. School-based programs should instead be linked with non-security efforts, families and policies that help change the overall social and cultural milieu in which young people live, leading to a permanent decrease in consumption and problems associated with alcohol among young people.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive research approach and has used a survey questionnaire to gather data. Data collected will be in the form of frequency, percentage, hence, quantitative by nature. The respondents are residents of Metro Manila, Philippines who are under 18 years old. Using Slovin's formula, the number of respondents for this study was derived from the total population of the National Capital Region which is 12,877,253 according to the 2015 census. Out of the total population, the sample size was computed with a 3% margin of error and 99% confidence level, whereas the result was divided to the number of cities and municipalities that compose NCR; Manila City - 110, Mandaluyong City - 108, Marikina City - 108, Pasig City - 108, Quezon City - 110, San Juan City - 108, Caloocan City - 110, Malabon City - 108, Navotas City - 108, Valenzuela City - 108, Las Pinas City - 108, Makati City - 108, Muntinlupa City - 108, Paranaque City - 108, Pasay City - 108, Pateros - 108, and Taguig City - 108. To specifically select the respondents who will represent each group, random sampling technique was utilized, whereas residents were selected based on who are able to be contacted first by the researcher without selectively picking among the entire population.

The researcher utilized an online self-constructed multiple-choice questionnaire to determine the compliance of establishments to Republic Act No. 9211, Section 9, and portions of the FDA Circular No. 2019-006 that states the prohibition of selling alcoholic beverages to minors. The responses of respondents in the self-constructed questionnaire will be measured through frequency and percentage, whereas response to the option "others" will undergo thematic analysis. Through the online questionnaire, needed information from the respondents will be collected. The researchers first communicated with potential respondents to ask for their consent and their parents, if necessary. After the consent has been given, they were asked to answer the questionnaire in the form of a Google form, which is accessed through a link that was sent to the respondents through Facebook Messenger and/or email. The entire process took the researcher a total of 72 days from March 18 to May 28, 2021.

This study has considered all ethical considerations in research. The researcher asked the consent from people who are under 18 years old to be the respondents and from their parents/guardians to allow them to answer the questionnaire. Voluntary participation has been expressed by the respondents when they agree to answer the research instrument; hence, no person was forced to do so. Participants' responses have been treated highly confidential and were not disclosed to anybody and have been kept anonymously when transferred to paper. Through an informed consent statement, the respondents were informed about the purpose and scope of this study, and the name of the researcher. The participants have been asked if they voluntarily allow the researchers to get their experiences in purchasing liquor and they were informed that without agreeing to this, they will not be obliged to answer the questionnaire. Moreover, it is also stated in the informed consent statement that they will not be receiving something in return of any kind by participating in this study.

Presentation of Results

Table 1

The usual reasons why minors purchase liquor

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Personal Consumption (<i>iinom ako; kasama ako sa iinom</i>).	445	24%
I am ordered by a family member or a friend (<i>Napag-uutusan lang ng kapamilya at kamaag-anak o kaibigan, ngunit ako ay hindi kasama sa iinom</i>).	1397	76%

Table 1 presents the usual reasons why minors buy liquor. This table clearly shows that the main motivation of minors in purchasing alcoholic beverages is the influence of their family and/or friends. It shows that majority of the respondents purchase liquor not for their own consumption but due to being ordered by a family member or friend. This indicates that family and friends may have a major influence on minors' liquor buying and drinking habits.

Table 2
Response of vendors / cashiers when encountered someone trying to buy liquor as observed by the respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
They ask me for an ID (<i>Hinahanapan ako ng ID</i>).	178	10%
I am asked of my age, but not required to present an ID (<i>Tinatanong ang edad ko pero hindi ako hinahanapan ng ID</i>).	741	40%
I am just asked of what I want to buy, and I will pay for it (<i>Tinatanong lang kung ano ang akong bibilhin at ito ay ibibigay sa akin, tapos ako ay magbabayad</i>).	923	50%

Table 2 presents the response of vendors / cashiers when encountered someone trying to buy liquor as observed by the respondents. Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents (50%) are not asked about their age by vendors/cashiers when they try to purchase liquors in stores, while 40% are asked about their age but are not asked to present a proof such as ID, and only 10% have encountered vendors/cashiers that requires an ID before making the purchase. This indicates that minors are more likely to be able to purchase liquor than be prohibited due to the lack of verification practices by the vendors/cashiers, which are mandated by the law.

Table 3
Establishments where minors usually purchase liquors

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Supermarket	179	10%
Convenience Stores	799	43%
Sari-Sari Stores	864	47%

Table 3 presents establishment where minors usually purchase liquors. This table presents that majority of the respondents (47%) purchase liquors in sari-sari stores, while 43% go to convenience stores, and 10% say supermarket. This indicates that sari-sari and convenience stores are the most accessible establishments to minor when it comes to their liquor purchase endeavors, and it could be assumed that they are more likely to successfully buy from these stores than in supermarkets.

Table 4
Experience of minors in buying liquor in supermarkets

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I was able to buy liquor from a supermarket (<i>Nakabili ako ng alak sa supermarket</i>).	509	28%
The cashier did not allow me to buy the liquor (<i>Hindi ako pinayagan ng cashier na bumili ng alak</i>).	595	32%
I have not tried buying liquor in a supermarket yet (<i>Hindi ko pa nasubukang bumili ng alak sa supermarket</i>).	738	40%

Table 4 presents the experience of minors in buying liquor in supermarkets. Table 4 shows that majority of the respondents (60%) have already tried buying liquor in a supermarket, whereas 46% of it was able to buy liquor from a supermarket, and the 54% failed to do so because the cashier did not allow them, while 40% have not yet tried it. This indicates that supermarkets in Metro Manila, particularly cashiers, most of the time implement what the law says, but there are instances when they do not, thus, clearly shows that they violate the provisions of the law and indirectly encourage minors to purchase and consume liquors.

Table 5
Experience of minors in buying liquor in convenience stores

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I was able to buy liquor from a convenience store (<i>Nakabili ako ng alak sa convenience store</i>).	536	29%
The cashier did not allow me to buy the liquor (<i>Hindi ako pinayagan ng cashier na bumili ng alak</i>).	684	37%
I have not tried buying liquor in a convenience store yet (<i>Hindi ko pa nasubukang bumili ng alak sa convenience store</i>).	622	34%

Table 5 presents the experience of minors in buying liquor in convenience stores. This table clearly shows that majority of the respondents (66%) have already tried buying liquor in a convenience store, whereas 44% of it was able to buy liquor, and the 56% failed to do so because the cashier did not allow them, while 43% have not yet tried it. This indicates that convenience stores in metro manila, particularly cashiers, most of the time implement what the law says, but there are instances when they do not, thus, clearly shows that they violate the provisions of the law and indirectly encourage minors to purchase and consume liquors.

Table 6
Experience of minors in buying liquor in sari-sari stores

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I was able to buy liquor from a sari-sari store (<i>Nakabili ako ng alak sa sari-sari store</i>).	677	37%
The cashier did not allow me to buy the liquor (<i>Hindi ako pinayagan ng cashier na bumili ng alak</i>).	565	31%
I have not tried buying liquor in a sari-sari store yet (<i>Hindi ko pa nasubukang bumili ng alak sa sari-sari store</i>).	600	32%

Table 6 presents the experience of minors in buying liquor in sari-sari stores. This table clearly shows that majority of the respondents (68%) have already tried buying liquor in a Sari-Sari store, whereas 55% of it was able to buy liquor, and the 45% failed to do so because the vendor did not allow them, while 32% have not yet tried it. This indicates that Sari-Sari stores in metro manila, particularly the vendors, most of the time do not implement what the law says, but there are instances when they do, thus, clearly shows that they violate the provisions of the law and indirectly encourage minors to purchase and consume liquors.

In a very short interview, the researcher have also found out that 936 (51%) of the respondents have experienced being able to buy liquor and failed to do so sometimes in supermarkets, while 1,008 (55%) have experienced the same in convenience stores, and 1154 (63%) have the same experience in Sari-Sari stores. With these, they were asked what is more frequent, being successful or being prohibited in buying liquor in the stores.

Table 7
Experience of minors on the frequency of being successful and being prohibited in buying liquor in supermarkets

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I am being allowed to buy liquor more often than to be prohibited by the cashier (<i>Mas madalas iyong pagkakataon na nakakabili ako ng alak kaysa sa mga pagkakataon na hindi pinapayagan ng cashier</i>).	412	44%
I am being prohibited by the cashier to buy liquor more often than to be allowed (<i>Mas madalas iyong mga pagkakataon na hindi ako nakakabili ng alak dahil pinagbabawalan ako ng cashier kaysa sa mga pagkakataon na ako ay nakakabili</i>).	524	56%

Table 7 presents the experience of minors on the frequency of being successful and being prohibited in buying liquor in supermarkets. This table shows that the frequency of minors being prohibited by cashiers in buying liquors in supermarkets (56%) is higher than instances when they are able to successfully purchase one (44%). This indicates that despite of the violation by the supermarket, minors are still more likely to be prohibited to buy liquors by cashiers in supermarkets in Metro Manila than to be allowed to do so.

Table 8
Experience of minors on the frequency of being successful and being prohibited in buying liquor in convenience stores

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I am being allowed to buy liquor more often than to be prohibited by the cashier (<i>Mas madalas iyong pagkakataon na nakakabili ako ng alak kaysa sa mga pagkakataon na hindi pinapayagan ng cashier</i>).	532	53%
I am being prohibited by the cashier to buy liquor more often than to be allowed (<i>Mas madalas iyong mga pagkakataon na hindi ako nakakabili ng alak dahil pinagbabawalan ako ng cashier kaysa sa mga pagkakataon na ako ay nakakabili</i>).	476	47%

Table 8 presents the experience of minors on the frequency of being successful and being prohibited in buying liquor in convenience stores. Table 8 clearly presents that the frequency of minors being able to successfully purchase liquor in convenience stores (53%) is higher than instances when they are being prohibited by cashiers (47%). This indicates that convenience stores despite of instances where they implement the law, their violation is more often; hence, minors are more likely to be able to successfully purchase liquor in convenience stores in Metro Manila than to be prohibited by the cashiers to do so.

Table 9
Experience of minors on the frequency of being successful and being prohibited in buying liquor in sari-sari stores

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I am being allowed to buy liquor more often than to be prohibited by the cashier (<i>Mas madalas iyong pagkakataon na nakakabili ako ng alak kaysa sa mga pagkakataon na hindi pinapayagan ng cashier</i>).	692	60%
I am being prohibited by the cashier to buy liquor more often than to be allowed (<i>Mas madalas iyong mga pagkakataon na hindi ako nakakabili ng alak dahil pinagbabawalan ako ng cashier kaysa sa mga pagkakataon na ako ay nakakabili</i>).	462	40%

Table 9 presents the experience of minors on the frequency of being successful and being prohibited in buying liquor in sari-sari stores. Table 9 shows that the frequency of minors being able to successfully purchase liquor in sari-sari stores (60%) is higher than instances when they are being prohibited by vendors (40%). This indicates that sari-sari stores despite of instances where they implement the law, their violation is more often; hence, minors are more likely to be able to successfully purchase liquor in sari-sari stores in Metro Manila than to be prohibited by the vendors to do so.

Figure 1 Awareness of respondents towards the prohibition of selling and buying liquors to and among minors

Figure 1 presents the awareness of respondents towards the prohibition of selling and buying liquors to and among minors. Figure 1 clearly shows that majority (63%) of the respondents are aware that they are not allowed to buy liquors and that stores should not allow them according to the law, while only 37% are unaware. This indicates that there is an inconsistency between the awareness and behavior of residents in Metro Manila as minors continue to purchase liquors in stores despite knowing that it illegal.

Summary of Findings

The researcher found out that majority of the respondents are aware that they are prohibited by the law to buy alcoholic beverage, however, there has been inconsistency between their awareness and behavior as they still do it. Though some minors purchase liquor for their own consumption, majority do it for their family and/or friends. It was determined that majority of minors who goes to stores to buy alcoholic beverages do it because they are ordered by a family member or friend and not for his/her own consumption.

It was also discovered that in most cases, when minors try to buy alcoholic beverages, vendors/cashiers just ask them what they wish to buy and let them pay for it without verifying their age, and this is usually observed in sari-sari and convenience stores as minors tends to purchase such products on these types of stores more often. Moreover, majority of the respondents have been determined to have experienced being allowed and not being permitted by the vendors/cashiers to purchase liquors in supermarkets, convenience stores, and sari-sari stores, however, it has been found out that the frequency of minor being allowed to purchase such products were higher than instances when they were prohibited in sari-sari stores and convenience stores compared in supermarket where the frequency of incidents where minor were not permitted is higher. Furthermore, the highest frequency of such incidents has been recorded in sari-sari stores.

Conclusion

Through the findings of this study, the researcher hereby concludes that family and friends are the main motivation why minors get into drinking alcoholic beverages. It is also assumed that minors are more likely to be able to purchase liquor than be prohibited due to the lack of age verification practices by the vendors/ cashiers, which are mandated by the law. The presence and the extended business hours of sari-sari stores and convenience stores, which is sometimes 24 hours is also concluded as the reason why minors tend to go to them to purchase liquor, likewise, one of the results of this study, that they are more likely to successfully buy from these stores than in supermarkets. It shows that the frequency of minors being able to purchase liquors is the highest in sari-sari stores, nevertheless, all types of stores in this study have been determined as non-compliant with the law and policy, hence, should undergo investigation, which will eventually lead to interventions that would ensure compliance to the law. Lastly, the inconsistency between the awareness and behavior minors towards the purchase of liquor and the law is assumed also as a result of the weak implementation of the law in these stores.

Recommendations

Inspired by the findings of this study, the following recommendations are presented:

- The executive branch of the government is hereby recommended to organize regular seminars for managers and employees of businesses that sell alcoholic beverages to promote awareness towards the provisions of the law and policy, likewise, for minors and their parents through schools and communities.
- Community leaders are hereby recommended to design a program that will teach parents about the law and their responsibility as parents to guide their children to a better future and not to bad habits.
- Law enforcement agencies are hereby recommended to undergo training on how to strengthen the implementation of the law, which will result to disciplined communities and law-abiding citizens.
- If this practice continues despite of such interventions, ratification towards a stronger law is a must, otherwise, the law and policy will be useless.

References

- Acosta, P. (2018, October 14). *Sale of liquor to minors*. The Manila Times. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2018/10/14/legal-advice/dearpao/sale-of-liquor-to-minors/451945>
- Alaniz, M. L., & Wilkes, C. (1998). Pro-drinking messages and message environments for young adults: The case of alcohol industry advertising in African American, Latino, and Native American communities. *Journal of Public Health Policy, 19*(4), 447-472. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3343076>
- Barry, A. E., Johnson, E., Rabre, A., Darville, G., Donovan, K. M., & Efunbumi, O. (2015). Underage access to online alcohol marketing content: A YouTube case study. *Alcohol and Alcoholism, 50*(1), 89-94. <https://doi.org/10.1093/alcalc/agu078>
- Berey, B. L., Loparco, C., Leeman, R. F., & Grube, J. W. (2017). The myriad influences of alcohol advertising on adolescent drinking. *Current Addiction Reports, 4*(2), 172-183. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40429-017-0146-y>
- Cerna, L. (2013). The nature of policy change and implementation: A review of different theoretical approaches. In *Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) report* (pp. 492-502). <https://www.oecd.org/education/ceri/The%20Nature%20of%20Policy%20Change%20and%20Implementation.pdf>
- Cook, R. L., Chung, T., Kelly, T. M., & Clark, D. B. (2005). Alcohol screening in young persons attending a sexually transmitted disease clinic: Comparison of AUDIT, CRAFFT, and CAGE instruments. *Journal of General Internal Medicine, 20*(1), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-1497.2005.40052.x>
- Cook, S. H., Bauermeister, J. A., Gordon-Messer, D., & Zimmerman, M. A. (2013). Online network influences on emerging adults' alcohol and drug use. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence, 42*(11), 1674-1686. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-012-9869-1>
- Dawson, D. A., Smith, S. M., Saha, T. D., Rubinsky, A. D., & Grant, B. F. (2012). Comparative performance of the AUDIT-C in screening for DSM-IV and DSM-5 alcohol use disorders. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence, 126*(3), 384-388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2012.05.029>
- De Vega, A. (2018, May 28). List of non-compliant firms released. Department of Labor and Employment. <https://www.dole.gov.ph/news/list-of-non-compliant-firms-released/>
- Domingo, R. E. D. (2019, September 24). *Guidelines in commercial display, selling, promotion, and advertising of alcoholic beverages and beverages that contain alcohol*. FDA Circular No. 2019-006. Food and Drug Administration. <https://www.fda.gov/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/FDA-Circular-No.-2019-006.pdf>
- Esser, M. B., & Jernigan, D. H. (2018). Policy approaches for regulating alcohol marketing in a global context: A public health perspective. *Annual Review of Public Health, 39*, 385-401. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-040617-014711>
- Grenard, J. L., Dent, C. W., & Stacy, A. W. (2013). Exposure to alcohol advertisements and teenage alcohol-related problems. *Pediatrics, 131*(2), e369-e379. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2012-1480>

- Gruber, E., DiClemente, R. J., Anderson, M. M., & Lodico, M. (1996). Early drinking onset and its association with alcohol use and problem behavior in late adolescence. *Preventive Medicine, 25* (3), 293-300. <https://doi.org/10.1006/pmed.1996.0059>
- Kabagani, L. J. (2020, December 9). *Business permit processing in Pasay goes online*. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1124288>
- Komro, K. A. (2018). Preventing risk for “deaths of despair” among American Indian youths: Unanswered questions for future research. *American Journal of Public Health, 108*(8), 973-974. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2018.304522>
- Komro, K. A., Stigler, M. H., & Perry, C. L. (2005). Comprehensive approaches to prevent adolescent drinking and related problems. In M. Galanter, C. Lowman, G. M. Boyd, V. B. Faden, E. Witt, & Dolly Lagressa (Eds.), *Alcohol problems in adolescents and young adults* (pp. 207-224). Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers.
- Koordeman, R., Anschutz, D. J., & Engels, R. C. (2012). The effect of alcohol advertising on immediate alcohol consumption in college students: an experimental study. *Alcoholism: Clinical and Experimental Research, 36*(5), 874-880. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-0277.2011.01655.x>
- Lenhart, A. (2015, April 9). *Teens, social media & technology overview 2015*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2015/04/09/teens-social-media-technology-2015/>
- Leyson, O. O. (2017, November 30). *Osmeña closes cousin's resto*. The Freeman. <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/the-freeman/20171130/281479276733954>
- Marquez, C. (2019, April 24). *Suspected gang member nabbed for robbery in Manila*. Philippine Daily Inquirer. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1110210/suspected-gang-member-nabbed-for-robbery-in-manila>
- Mocon-Ciriaco, C. (2020, December 17). *Pinoy start young, are top gin and beer drinkers, study says*. Business Mirror. <https://businessmirror.com.ph/2020/12/17/pinoys-start-young-are-top-gin-and-beer-drinkers-study-says/>
- Nhean, S., Nyborn, J., Hinchey, D., Valerio, H., Kinzel, K., Siegel, M., & Jernigan, D. H. (2014). The frequency of company-sponsored alcohol brand-related sites on Facebook™-2012. *Substance Use & Misuse, 49*(7), 779-782. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10826084.2014.880177>
- Official Gazette. (2003, June 23). *Republic Act No. 9211 – An act regulating the packaging, use, sale, distribution and advertisements of tobacco products and for other purposes*. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2003/06/23/republic-act-no-9211/>
- Orellana, F. (2019, October 8). *Isetann Recto faces possible shutdown due to lack of business permit*. Philippine Daily Inquirer. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1175159/isetann-recto-faces-possible-shutdown-due-to-lack-of-business-permit>
- Petratis, J., Flay, B. R., & Miller, T. Q. (1995). Reviewing theories of adolescent substance use: Organizing pieces in the puzzle. *Psychological Bulletin, 117*(1), 67-86. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.117.1.67>
- Sudhinaraset, M., Wigglesworth, C., & Takeuchi, D. T. (2016). Social and cultural contexts of alcohol use: Influences in a social-ecological framework. *Alcohol Research: Current Reviews, 38* (1), 35-45.
- Swahn, M., Haberlen, M., & Palmier, J. B. (2014). Alcohol and drug use and other high-risk behaviors among youth in the slums of Kampala, Uganda: Perceptions and contexts obtained through focus groups. *International Journal of Alcohol and Drug Research, 3*(4), 289-295. <https://doi.org/10.7895/ijadr.v3i4.171>
- Swahn, M. H., Palmier, J. B., Benegas-Segarra, A., & Sinson, F. A. (2013). Alcohol marketing and drunkenness among students in the Philippines: findings from the nationally representative Global School-based Student Health Survey. *BMC Public Health, 13*, 1159. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-1159>
- Tanski, S. E., McClure, A. C., Jernigan, D. H., & Sargent, J. D. (2011). Alcohol brand preference and binge drinking among adolescents. *Archives of Pediatrics & Adolescent Medicine, 165* (7), 675-676. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpediatrics.2011.113>
- The Manila Times. (2019, January 22). *Physical injury most committed crime by minors in 2018-police*. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2019/01/22/latest-stories/breakingnews/physical-injury-most-committed-crime-by-minors-in-2018-police/500378>
- Valbuena, J. P. (2006). *Alcohol and media: The situation in the Philippines*. Health Action Information Network. <https://doksi.net/en/get.php?lid=26562>
- World Health Organization. (2019). *Global status report on alcohol and health 2018*. World Health Organization.